

SoC BASED MODERN HYBRID TEST COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Test vector compression is an emerging trend in the field of VLSI testing. According to these trends, increasing test data volume is one of the biggest challenges in the testing industry. In order to reduce on-chip storage as well as testing time, the large volume of test data input is compressed in hybrid manner before being downloaded into the processor. Test compression involves compressing the large volumes of test data to small test sets that fit in the memory of Automatic Test Equipment. As the density of VLSI circuit increases, high test quality in smaller geometries can be achieved only through more test patterns. So it is essential to integrate dedicated test logic on a chip called Automatic Test Equipment for testing. But this tester has limited speed, memory and I/O channels. The test data bandwidth between the tester and the chip is small which is the bottleneck in determining how fast the testing process. To overcome these limitations of the Automatic Test Equipment (ATE), a new hybrid test vector compression technique is proposed. The test compression ratio is increased and is experimentally verified with the benchmark circuits.

INTRODUCTION

Very large-scale integration has added enormous complexity to the process of testing integrated circuits, thereby increasing the cost of electronic components. The complexity of testing system-on-a-chip (SOC) integrated circuit has also been considerably enhanced, because of the large number of intellectual property (IP) cores that are now being used on a single piece of silicon. In order to effectively test these systems, each intellectual property(IP) core must be adequately exercised with a set of pre computed test patterns as provided by the core vendor(Fig.1).

Although the modern System-on-a-Chip (SoC) incorporates many functions, they were affected by several test challenges. Huge test data volume is one of the major problems for the SoC vendors. Because the huge test data volume not only exceeds the commercial Automatic Test Equipment (ATE) memory and I/O channel capacity, it also increases the testing time and test power. Increase in test time, memory and power cause a direct impact on test cost and time to market. So the vendors are in a situation to reduce the volume of test data.Reduction of test data gathers the attention of all the SoC designers for the past several years.The methods which are used to reduce the amount of test data that is stored in the ATE memory are test vector compaction and test data compression.

Fig. 1. A conventional architecture for SOC testing

Many test data compression techniques have been proposed so far to reduce the test data volume and improve the transmission efficiency between the ATE and SoC. The compression technique is used to condense the test data and is stored in ATE memory. Through the test channels the compressed data are transferred to SoC. An onchip decoder is used to retrieve the original test data without any loss and is scanned serially.

In particular, embedded test pattern generators (TPG) and test response evaluators (TRE) can provide a high bandwidth for handling test data while only a low-bandwidth connection to a lightweight ATE is required

Fig 2: Reducing bandwidth for external access with BIST

However, if the system contains intellectual property (IP) blocks coming only with a set T of test patterns, then techniques are required to store the given test set T in a compact representation and regenerate it during test. For this task compression codes offer a two-fold solution:

- (1) The test data volume can be greatly reduced by simple encoding and decoding procedures.
- (2) As illustrated in Fig 3, there is a natural option for test resource partitioning, i.e. it is sufficient to implement the decoder on chip, and the encoded test data can be stored either on or off chip.

Fig 3: Store-and-generate approach for test pattern generation.

RELATED WORK

Since test data compression has several compression techniques have been proposed in the bygone years to reduce the test data volume. Some of them are statistical coding selective Huffman coding , Tunstall coding , LZW coding , heterogeneous compression technique , FDR coding , run length Huffman coding , multilevel Huffman coding , Bitmask and Dictionary Selection Methods and variable to variable Huffman coding .

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Run-Length coding

In variable-to-fixed coding, the original test cubes are partitioned into variable length symbols, and the codewords are each b-bits long. In Run-Length coding, one particular variable-to-fixed coding scheme, the symbols consist of runs of consecutive 0's or 1's , test compression based on a Run-Length code was proposed. An example of a Three-bit Run-Length code for runs of 0's is given in Table 4.1. Each codeword is 3 bits long and encodes different length runs of 0's.

As an example, the sequence 001 0001 01 0000001 1 000001 can be encoded into 010 011 001 110 000 101, which is a reduction from 23 bits to 18 bits. For very long runs of 0's (longer than 7), codeword 111 can be used repeatedly as needed. Note that only data with an unbalanced number of 0's and 1's can be efficiently compressed by a run-length code.

Test compression based on a Run-Length code using a cyclical scan architecture as shown in Fig 4 The cyclical scan architecture XORs the data currently being shifted in with the previous test vector. Thus, instead of applying the original test set, $T_D = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_n\}$, difference vector set, $T_{diff} = \{t_1, t_1 \text{ XOR } t_2, t_2 \text{ XOR } t_3, \dots, t_{n-1} \text{ XOR } t_n\}$, is applied instead.

Table 1 :Three-bit Run-Length code

Symbol	Codeword
1	0 0 0
0 1	0 0 1
0 0 1	0 1 0
0 0 0 1	0 1 1
0 0 0 0 1	1 0 0
0 0 0 0 0 1	1 0 1
0 0 0 0 0 0 1	1 1 0
0 0 0 0 0 0 0	1 1 1

Fig 4: Cyclical scan architecture for applying difference vectors

Golomb coding

In variable-to-variable coding, both the symbols and codewords have variable length. A Golomb code is a variable-to-variable code that evolved from the Run-Length code. To construct a Golomb code, a specific parameter m , called the group size (usually a power of 2), is first chosen. All the Run-Lengths are divided into groups of size m denoted by A_1, A_2, A_3, \dots . The set of Run-Lengths $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1\}$ form the first group A_1 , the set of Run-Lengths $\{m, m+1, \dots, 2m\}$ form the second group A_2 , and so on.

Each codeword of a Golomb code consists of two parts:

1. Group Prefix
2. Tail

Table 2: Golomb code with four Run-Lengths for each group

Group	Run-Length	Group Prefix	Tail	Codeword
A_1	0	0	00	000
	1		01	001
	2		10	010
	3		11	011
A_2	4	10	00	1000
	5		01	1001
	6		10	1010
	7		11	1011
A_3	8	110	00	11000
	9		01	11001
	10		10	11010
	11		11	11011
...

A Run-Length l that belongs to group A_k is assigned a group prefix $(k-1)$ of ones followed by a zero. The tail is an index of the Run-Length in a group. If m is chosen to be a power of 2 (i.e., $m = 2^N$ for some integer N), then each group contains 2^N members, and a $\log_2 m$ -bit-long sequence (tail) can uniquely identify each member within the group. Table show an example of Golomb code in which each group contains four Run-Lengths.

Table 3 : Proposed hybrid technique

Group	Run-Length	Group Prefix	Tail	Codeword
A1	0	0	0	00
	1		1	01
	2	1	0	10
	3		1	11
A2	4	0	00	000
	5		01	001
	6		10	010
	7		11	011
	8	1	00	100
	9		01	101
	10		10	110
	11		11	111
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By combining the properties of Run-length and Golomb coding the above proposed hybrid technique Table are developed. This can be used for developing both runs of 0's and 1's. This table is greatly used to compress the number of bits that are required to test the benchmark circuits.

The data flows through the lossless data compression and decompression algorithm, the input data is first compressed. The first data compression codes that researchers investigated for compressing scan vectors encoded runs of repeated values. The proposed a scheme based on run-length codes that encoded runs of 0s using fixed-length code words. To increase the prevalence of runs of 0s, this scheme uses a cyclical scan architecture to allow the application of difference vectors where the difference vector between test cubes t_1 and t_2 is equal to $t_1 \approx t_2$. Careful ordering of the test cubes maximizes the number of 0s in the difference vectors, thereby improving the effectiveness of run-length coding. A technique based on Golomb codes that encode runs of 0s with variable-length code words. The use of variable-length code words allows efficient encoding of longer runs, although it requires a synchronization mechanism between the tester and the chip.

RESULTS ON SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

To demonstrate the feasibility and comparative effectiveness of the proposed test data compaction scheme, independent simulations were conducted on various ISCAS 85 combinational benchmark circuits. The proposed hybrid compression technique is compared with previous techniques such as Run-length coding and Golomb coding. Here the compression ratio of hybrid technique is higher than the normal compression schemes. The percentage data compression was computed as follows:

% Compression

$$\frac{\text{Original Bits} - \text{Compressed Bits}}{\text{Original Bits}} \times 100.$$

The combinational circuits results are obtained by applying the proposed coding techniques from ISCAS 85 combinational benchmark circuits are presented in Table 4. In these circuits, the maximum compression was estimated for circuit c1908 as 65.55% and minimum amount of compression was for circuit c1355 at about 50.01%.

Table 5: ISCAS'85 Circuit Characteristics

S.No	Circuit Name	No.of Inputs	No.of Outputs
1.	c17	5	2
2.	c432	36	7
3.	c499	41	32
4.	c1908	33	25
5.	c1355	31	32
6.	c6288	32	32

Finally, Figure 6 shows the comparative compression results while using Run-Length, Golomb coding and proposed coding method. Figure 6 shows graphically the test vector compression results for several ISCAS 85 combinational benchmark circuits. Figure 6 shows the comparative compression results obtained from ISCAS 85 combinational benchmark circuits computed by employing the proposed technique along with one of the most recent methods.

The benchmark circuit C432 have 36 bit Original Bits they are

000001 00001 00000001 0000001 0001 0001 01

Compressed Bits

Run-Length Coding :101 100 111 110 011 011 001

Golomb Coding :1001 1000 1011 1010 011 011 001

Hybrid Method :101 100 111 110 11 11 01(18 bits)

% Compression = $[36-18/36]$

% compression= (50.01%)

Table 4: Test vector compression results for several ISCAS'85

Circuit Name	No. of Inputs	No. of Outputs	Compression % Run-Length	Compression % Golomb	Compression % Proposed
c432	36	7	41.66	30.50	50.01
c499	41	32	34.14	29.51	64.90
c1908	33	25	50.01	38.88	65.55
c1355	41	32	41.66	22.22	57.22
c6282	32	32	49.45	41.72	59.18

Fig 5: Test Compression Results for C432

ISCAS'85 Benchmark Circuits

Fig 6: Test compression results for several ISCAS 85 benchmark circuits

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The Hybrid test compression technique which combines both Run-Length and Golomb coding is implemented. Also the compression ratio is measured for each coding technique. The results are obtained by applying the proposed coding technique from ISCAS'85 benchmark circuits. In these ISCAS'85 combinational benchmark circuits the highest compression was obtained for circuit c1908, which is 66.55%, while the lowest amount of compression was calculated for the circuit c432 as 50.01%. The delay obtained in proposed system is about 100ns. The Hybrid test vector compression is implemented through ModelSim 6.6d version and the functionality of each test compression technique was verified. Among these three, Hybrid compression produces more reduction in test vector than the normal individual coding schemes.

In future, Hybrid compression based on Linear and Broadcast scan based techniques can be developed for ISCAS'85 and ISCAS'89 benchmark circuits. For the same circuits, the analysis of area overhead and delay will be done. Also the maximum reduction in test vector, tester memory space and test vector transfer time will be achieved with the help of proposed Hybrid test compression technique

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